

A Case Study of Causes and Injury Pattern on Road Accident in Dhaka

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Bangladesh is a typical country for the car crash study among the developing nations due to the unique complex traffic environment. The aim of this study is to investigate the causes of road accidents and the injury pattern of road accidents in Dhaka for the last 11 years. The secondary data were first collected and investigated, then the primary parameters of the traffic accident like the accident time and crash types were analyzed through the comparison and main factor analysis. Results show that the human factor is the main cause of the car crash, which accounts for more than 95% of the whole accidents. This means the traffic rule education should be further improved to reduce the influence of human. Meanwhile, the noontime is not suitable for road users throughout the week in terms of the accident risk. Though the injury consequence is not much, the rear impact occupies the most percentage. This study can be a reference for the follow-up road accident researches for statistical analysis.

Keywords: TRAFFIC ACCIDENT, INJURY PATTERN, CRASH CAUSES, DATA INVESTIGATION

1. Introduction

Bangladesh is located in South Asia with a population of 165,854,811 according to world meter elaboration of the latest data from the United Nations (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bangladesh>). The length of major roads in Bangladesh is about 21,269 km. Among these, about 3,538 km are national highways, 4,276 km are regional roads, and 13,455 km are feeder roads (H. M. AHSAN1*, January 2012). The transportation system

of Bangladesh is complex and heterogeneous with both motorized vehicles (MVs) and non-motorized vehicles (NMVs). Meanwhile, Bangladesh is considered as one of the least motorized countries in the world [1]. Thus, the study on causes and injury pattern of road accident in Bangladesh can be an important reference to the improvement of traffic safety for most developing nations.

All aspects of a country's development required good transportation system construction. Although most traffic accidents happened on the roadway, it was still the most popular and important transportation system for low-income country [2]. Bangladesh had mostly a mixed traffic system, and most of the road users are pedestrians, buses, trucks, pickup vans, private cars, motor vehicles, and auto rickshaws, which means the traffic environment is very complex. Based on statistical data, Mamun pointed out that the fatality rate of road traffic accidents in Bangladesh was extremely high, which was 0.6% [3].

According to a World Bank analysis, average traffic speed in Dhaka has dropped from 21 kilometer to 7 kilometer per hour over the last 10 years. Congestion in the capital kills about 3.2million working hours every day. Road accidents in Bangladesh have reached an epidemic level with over 1,000 people dead in road crashes in the first three months of this year [6].

Road accident is one of the biggest causes of unnatural deaths in Bangladesh. In fact, the country has one of the highest rates of death from road crashes in the world, according to World Bank statistics. Road accident in particular is now acknowledged to be a global phenomenon with authorities in virtually all countries of the world concerned about the growth in the number of people killed and seriously injured on their roads. The causes of street accidents are reckless driving, brake failures of vehicles, over-taking of one vehicle by another, driving by unskilled drivers. Over loading of vehicles is another reason for accidents. Another reason is violation of traffic rules.

As the number of registered vehicles increased, the accidents also increased day by day in Bangladesh. Any accident might cause various problems. Among them, vehicle damages, road damages, human injuries, and loss of valuable assets are the common consequences. As Dhaka was the capital of Bangladesh and the most densely populated city, many accidents happened every day in Dhaka city. In terms of Bangladesh, road accident was a very normal daily activity. More than 12 accidents happened within a single day alongside dead innocent people in Bangladesh. The prime issues for these accidents where the road system was not well enough, the quality of vehicles and drivers were not up to the mark at all. Moreover, the pedestrians were not aware, and they do not usually follow the traffic rules and regulations. It had been an alarming issue in Bangladesh over the past few years and had become a national problem.

The objective of this study is to find out the causes and injury pattern of road accidents in Dhaka. The specific objective of this study identifies the causes of road accidents and the injury pattern of road accidents in Dhaka

by analyzing the secondary data of the last 11 years from 2010 to 2020. Accident Data collated from Dhaka metro Politian police head coaters (DMP). This study also does some interviews with police man, drivers and pedestrians. The main objective of this study is to find out the causes of accidents and injuries in Dhaka city. The total number of accidents, deaths, injuries and the total number of vehicle registrations in Dhaka city in the last 11 years has been extracted. It has been found out that the number of accidents in Dhaka city is 24 hours in a week.

2. Literature Review

The World Health Organization (WHO) report that more than one million people die dowing to traffic accidents every year. It also pointed out that traffic accidents were the most frequent cause of death for adolescents and youth. Moreover, developing countries around the world would suffer 65 billion dollars in economic losses because of traffic accidents each year. Statistics from the Accident Research Institute (ARI) showed that pedestrian mortality is abnormally high, which is 77% [7]. More than a million people dies in road crashes annually all over the world. This phenomenon is the leading cause of death among young people aged 18-24, according to WHO. At this rate, this will become the 7th major reason for death of peoples of all ages by 2030. The estimated cost of road accidents in lower and middle-income countries is around 65 billion dollars (CDC). In Dhaka city, the cost is about 1.95 billion dollars which is 2% of our GDP. (Chakraborty, 2017)

Environmental factors and stress were responsible for major road traffic accidents. Other crucial factors such as the condition of the vehicle, protective measures, operational error and time/place of the accident determined the fatalities and the severity of the accidents. Human error was seemingly the main reason for most vehicular accidents. Investigation on the role of human in the traffic system was the focus of dealing with road safety problems. The skill of the driver and traffic scenes are other important factors that affect car impacts. Among these, human error is due to the pressure of economic or family issues. This mentality makes them cause road accidents, which is one of the reasons for their slow response. Carelessness is one of the main causes of road accidents in the world. Specifically, some people may use a mobile phone while driving, neglecting the red signal in traffic signals, which emerges from a side road into the path of another vehicle. Over speeding is one of the reasons as the severity of injury increases with impact velocity, and the lack of head protection accounts for the most severe but preventable injuries. Inexperienced drivers and drivers without proper training as well as insufficient knowledge of traffic signs tend to increase the number of road traffic accidents. Another important cause for an alarming growth in the number of road accidents is drunk driving. Under the influence of alcohol and other intoxicating substances, the drivers lose self-consciousness and control over the vehicle, which ultimately forms the reason for accidents. Lack of sensitivity and responsibility on the part of state authorities is also one of the reasons. The human sensibility and life respecting emotions of state authorities, to look into the conditions on the roads, such as the failure of traffic

lights, which can also lead to accidents if not properly maintained [8].

As the occurrence of accidents are always unpredictable, so some of them are harmful to the people and the society. Especially road traffic accidents were a global phenomenon, and it had become an issue that needed to solve urgently. Governments of all countries paid close attention to the number of casualties caused by traffic accidents [9]. Generally, accidents are more likely to occur on roads where cars, buses, bicycles and pedestrians are mixed. However, the method of engineering measurements could reduce the accident and injury possibility [10]. In Bangladesh and other developing countries, due to urban construction and population reasons, the traffic situation was very complicated. Different kinds of vehicles were running on the road at the same time, and there was no separation between motor vehicle lanes and non-motor vehicle lanes. Under this traffic situation, the traffic capacity was calculated by the usual method was not feasible. The average speed of highways also varied greatly, and there were mainly the following dependent factors: the size of the vehicle, weather factors, driver, and the traffic situation. Spot speed referred to the instantaneous speed of the vehicle at a specific location, which was a common criterion for accident studies under varied situations [11].

Previously, many studies on the influence factors of vehicle-pedestrian impacts have been carried out. These studies were based on statistics from developed countries, and studies on developing countries were insufficient. The road environment and pedestrian behavior were different in developed and developing countries [12]. Thus, it was necessary to conduct the study in developing countries. From 2010 to 2020, the number of people killed and injured from traffic accidents in Dhaka continued to increase. In all traffic accidents, 85% of the victims were male, and most of them were 20-39 years old (<https://trid.trb.org/view/514118>). Pedestrians tended to have the highest level of injuries. The death rate of pedestrians in traffic accidents was more than half. 17% of accidents were auto-rickshaw accidents, and 11% of victims using a rickshaw died during this kind of accident. Besides, bus and truck accidents caused 5% of the total deaths. Because of insufficient sidewalk construction and neglect of pedestrians, pedestrian deaths account for a very higher proportion than that in developed countries [13].

In Dhaka, a large number of people died and were seriously injured by road accidents every year for various reasons. It was found that there is a gap in the study on the causes and injury patterns of road accident in Dhaka. It is necessary to find out the real causes and actual injury patterns of road accidents in Dhaka.

3.Theoretical Background

3.1 Data

The study was carried out by applying both the quantitative and qualitative approaches of social research. The quantitative data and qualitative information were triangulated to get a comprehensive. Total vehicle

registered and road accident crash data from 2010 to 2020 in Bangladesh and Dhaka were provided by the Accident research institute at the Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BRTA). Dhaka City is surrounded by rivers that restrict the natural growth of the city in the horizontal direction. Dhaka city area is under jurisdiction of different authorities that are known as Dhaka North and South City Corporations (DCC), Dhaka Metropolitan Area (DMA), Dhaka Statistical Metropolitan Area (DSMA) and Dhaka Metropolitan Development Plan (DMDP) area. The study area covered all the Dhaka metropolitan area.

The study used both qualitative and quantitative methods. The primary and secondary data were collected from the related stakeholders using the data entry method, key informant interview, and in-depth case studies of the drivers, pedestrians, traffic policies, and concerns officials of Ministries/Divisions/Agencies. Specifically, the method of comparative analysis, grouping analysis, and time series analysis were used. The comparative analysis method was used to investigate road accidents in different income level countries. The grouping analysis method was used to investigate the main causes of the accident, and the accident of week and time was studied with the help of the time series analysis method.

3.2 Methodology

From the data portal of Bangladesh government, we see the total road accidents and casualty statistics from 2010-2020. It shows that, each year average around accidents 11,6 59 people, injury 7360 people and 4298 people deaths in Bangladesh. A Study on Pedestrian total road accident, injury and Deaths in Dhaka City Road Accidents average in road accidents in Bangladesh. It shows that, each year average around accidents 1349 people, injury 1022 people and 324 people deaths in Dhaka city. As the capital city, Dhaka has the largest locality with population of 165,854,811 according to World meter elaboration of the latest data from the United Nations. The accidents scenario in here is also severe. Almost every day we here about road crashes and deaths of people on the roads. In this paper we are trying to find out the trend and overall scenario of deaths, especially the death of the pedestrians. We will also try to find out how many accidents happened here because of poor traffic management and how many occurred due to the carelessness of pedestrians. Also, the trend in accident and death toll to be discussed here whether the rate is increasing or decreasing. How likely the pedestrians are subject to become a victim in these accidents will be the focusing point of the paper. And we will try to figure out in this study if the number of motor vehicle, population, urban literacy rate and transportation expenditure has any impact on these accidents over the year. This study used both qualitative and quantitative methods. The primary and secondary data were collected from the related stakeholders using the data entry method, key informant interview, and in-depth case studies of the drivers, pedestrians, traffic policies, and concerns officials of Ministries/Divisions/Agencies.

A data set has been prepared, and based on the study required, the tables, graphs, charts, and analysis have been done and tried to illustrate the real scenario of identifying the real causes and the actual injury patterns of road accident in Dhaka.

3.3 Data Analysis

This study has used the road total accidents, deaths, injuries, and impacts of the last 11 years from the year 2010 to 2020 of Dhaka. The study first presented all the registered vehicles, road accidents, deaths, and injury data of Bangladesh and showed road accidents, deaths, and injury data of Dhaka, then main cases road accident in Dhaka was shown and the main cause of accidents was discussed, accident severity, impact type of accident and impact type by percentage were all compared.

In order to understand the underlying reasons behind road accidents and features, road accident and injury data analysis were important. The proportion of road accidents and magnitude of fatality, casualty due to accidents, trends of road accidents in different reasons of road and factors.

The study has collected the monthly data and information for 11 years from the Dhaka Metropolitan Police with prior permission from the Additional Commissioner of Police (Traffic), DMP. This data are not publicly available. In addition, the author has conducted some interviews with the police man and also the pedestrians on the causes and injury patters of the road accident. So, it must have some uniqueness.

4.Result and Discussion

4.1 Reasons for road accident

The main cause of road accidents is excessive speed limit of vehicles. Attempting to overtake another moving vehicle at excessive speed with carelessness is one of the causes of road accidents. The police report also cited excessive speed and reckless driving as the cause of most of the accidents.

Excessive speed and overtaking: Excessive speed and overtaking of vehicles is blamed as one of the causes of road accidents. The police report also said that excessive speed and reckless driving of the drivers were responsible for the accident. There is also a lot of history of accidents when cars get on the bridge at high speeds.

Narrow roads: Most of the roads in Bangladesh are narrow. As a result, the number of road accidents is increasing day by day. The busiest routes from Dhaka are Dhaka-Arica and Dhaka-Chittagong highways. These roads are not wider than necessary. As a result, accidents and casualties are more in these two ways. Moreover, accidents often occur due to excessive traffic on narrow roads across the country.

Overloading: Overloading means carrying more goods than capacity. As a result, drivers often lose control and cause accidents.

Some reasons for the road accident are described below:

Over speed.

Competition with one another.

Risky over-taking.

Rough motorcycle driving without proper safety gears.

Not obeying the traffic rules and regulation.

Narrowness and bad condition of the road during most of the times.

Lack of foot over bridges and underpasses and no regular use of those existing by the people.

Fitness less/faulty vehicles running on the road.

Lack of quick & strict punishments to the accused drivers & owners of the vehicles in most cases.

Break failure by the vehicles.

Lack of speed breakers in right places like schools, college, market, hospitals, etc.

Negligence in duties by the traffic polices in some cases.

Driving with hurry for any reason or, patience less driving.

Lack of ideal bus stops.

Using a mobile phone while driving.

Driving in sleeping mood.

Driving by the drunk drivers.

Unconscious and careless driving without observing, right, left, front and back.

Driving on the wrong side.

Carrying too many passengers in the vehicle.

Improper road management system.

Faulty traffic signals by the traffic lights.

People not using footpath properly.

Too many roads' binds.

Drivers have the lack of knowledge/understanding about the traffic signals and symbols.

Guardian remain careless about his/her children while crossing and walking beside the roads.

Drivers don't have a clear idea about the road while driving according to his vehicle's capability and performance, especially in his hilly and bumpy roads.

Limitations in planned road construction/renovation procedure and works.

Sudden hard break by the front vehicle.

Not keeping enough gaps in between the vehicles while driving on road especially by the local buses.

Not following the lane while driving and frequent lane changing.

Crowd-full markets/sopping zone beside both side of the roads.

Issuance of driving license illegally.

4.2 Patterns of Injury

Road accident was a condition that could occur at any point and any moment which was dangerous for human life. Any part of the body could be seriously injured in a road accident. The following were some of the most common injuries suffered by motor vehicle accident victims. The issue of road safety in Dhaka was addressed. Injury and fatality rates had been increasing constantly, and the fatality rate had increased significantly in the

past 11 years in the Dhaka metropolitan area [13].

The only fatal loss in a road accident is when a person's limbs are amputated in a road accident and they become disabled for life. They can't go to work, and many lose their eyesight, can't see anything in the world for the rest of their lives, and are crippled in many more serious road accidents. Road accidents can cause a variety of injuries, such as, external injury, head and neck injury, face and Ent, chest, abdomen, upper limb, lower limb, spine, pelvis and brain injury.

The number of injuries and deaths in the population of Dhaka city has been steadily increasing in the last 11 years. The image above describes the different types of injuries in 2020. The various data of this injury have been taken from the Dhaka medical college and hospital. One year (2020) of data is discussed below, A total of 950 injuries last year (2020) Dhaka Metropolitan area. As shown in Figure 1, Most of all the external injury 23% (216), Head and Neck injury 16% (155) and the lowest Pelvis injury 4% and Spine injury 4%.

Figure 1: Patterns of Injury

4.3 Results

As we all know, road collision was an increasingly serious problem for low-income countries. Studies had also shown that although the number of road deaths in high-income countries was slowly declining, the situation in low-income countries was getting worse. As infectious diseases were increasingly controlled, the relative importance of road deaths and injuries had risen [14].

As the eighth most populous country in the world, Bangladesh is one of the countries with the highest population density globally. It was shown that high-, middle- and low-income countries account for the proportion of global population, registered vehicle and road traffic deaths (Figure 2). Mortality was high in low-income countries, which account for a much lower proportion of the registered vehicle population. The analysis revealed that the road accident casualty rate in Bangladesh was very high, Official statistics indicated that more than 85 deaths per 10,000 registered motor vehicles every year. Moreover, the number of registered motor vehicles was also increasing dramatically.

Figure 2. Global road accidents in different income level countries

In the last 11 years (2010 to 2020), there were 3,584,544 registered vehicles in Bangladesh (Table 1). In total of 128 thousand road traffic accidents occurred in the last 11 years. As a result, 47 thousand people died, and 80 thousand were injured. The number of accidents and deaths was fluctuating, but it has declined over the year. A road was a way on land between two places that has been paved or otherwise improved to allow travel by foot or some form of transportation, including a motor vehicle, trolley, bicycle or horse. Traffic accidents were affected by diverse road factors [11]. In terms of the registered motor vehicles (BRTA) in Bangladesh, the number was still going up. The highest number of motor vehicles registered happened in 2020. Over the past years, the highest accident number was captured in the year 2020 with a number of 15286, followed by the year 2018 for road accidents in Bangladesh (Figure 3).

Table 1: Motor vehicles and road accident reported casualties in Bangladesh

Year	Registered Motor Vehicles	Deaths	Injury	Total Accident
2010	161178	2847	6586	9433
2011	185386	2467	5537	8004
2012	160705	3137	5174	8311
2013	137109	3296	5465	8761
2014	160639	6303	8465	14768
2015	321215	5003	6197	11200
2016	416410	3412	8572	11984
2017	420398	4284	9112	13396
2018	497374	4317	10828	15145
2019	504130	5536	6425	11961
2020	620000	6686	8600	15286

Figure 3: Total accident from 2010 to 2020

To analysis what time and what days the rate of accident is high, middle, and low for 24 hours, a figure was shown (Figure 4). It is noted that 11 am on Sunday, Monday and Tuesday were the highest time for road accidents recorded in Dhaka city. Figure 3 of the whole week show the highest number of accidents on Friday, 5 times a day on Friday. The lowest number of accidents occur on Wednesdays and Saturdays are Bangladesh holidays which is why there are less accidents on Saturdays due to less traffic. This meant that the noontime is a dangerous time for the road users, which might be that more people will use the road at that time than the users in other time. And there was small number of accidents happened at the later night especially for the weekends. In the night, the middle night was special throughout the whole week due to the high rate of accident. The figure illustrated that there was a greater number of accidents in the morning time.

Figure 4: Accident chart of week and time of the day

Of all the road traffic accidents that occurred from 2010 to 2020 (Table 2), the accident data covering the years 2010 to 2020 for the study area were collected. In total, there were 3565 road accident death and 11244 road injuries found in Dhaka in the last 11 years. The death number was kept at a level of around 340 per year, though there was a downward trend. Meanwhile, the injury number was about 1020, which meant nearly the injury rate was 3 times as much as the death rate.

Table 2: Motor vehicles and road accident reported casualties in Dhaka

Year	Deaths	Injury	Total Accident
2010	347	1065	1412
2011	324	1206	1530
2012	367	867	1234
2013	307	980	1287
2014	306	1100	1406
2015	306	1030	1336
2016	278	908	1186
2017	274	848	1122
2018	339	1265	1604
2019	427	1025	1452
2020	290	950	1240

To explain why road accidents were a more common problem, data analysis was used (Table 3). According to the data of the last 11 years, the number of accidents due to human error and vehicles was high. Human error as the major cause of road crashes humans had limited information processing capabilities and must depend on three fallible psychological functions: perception, attention and memory. When a driver failed to avoid an accident because the situation exceeded these limitations, which was often referred to as "human error." Actually, it was often the circumstances that is principally responsible, not the driver's reaction to it. It was a well-known prejudice of human judgment to commit the "fundamental attribution error," human factors were seriously overestimated and environmental factors were seriously underestimated when attempting to explain the cause of the event. This table showed the total number of human error accidents in 2012 due to more than 426. Moreover, the total human error road accident total was 3569 in the last 11 years. Most of the vehicles in Bangladesh were not of good quality. These vehicles did not have enough safety systems, which caused many accidents for the vehicle. For the last 11 years, the total vehicle defected was 32.

Table 3. Main causes of the accident

MAIN CAUSE	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	TOTAL
Vehicle Defect	2	3	0	4	2	2	6	3	5	2	3	32
Road Defect	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	3

MAIN CAUSE	<i>2010</i>	<i>2011</i>	<i>2012</i>	<i>2013</i>	<i>2014</i>	<i>2015</i>	<i>2016</i>	<i>2017</i>	<i>2018</i>	<i>2019</i>	<i>2020</i>	TOTAL
Human Error	347	359	426	329	319	364	335	329	230	320	211	3569
Other	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
TOTAL	349	362	427	335	321	367	341	333	235	322	214	3606

Regarding the severity of traffic accidents and the consequences after the traffic accident (Table 4), the sum total of fatal accidents was 2141 in the last 11 years, though the number had decreased significantly. Simple injury accident total was 178, which showed the same trend as the fatal injury. The total number of Grievous accidents was 565 as well as the motor impact was 224, and they both kept at the same level through the last 11 years.

Table 4. Accident severity

ACCIDENT SEVERITY	<i>2010</i>	<i>2011</i>	<i>2012</i>	<i>2013</i>	<i>2014</i>	<i>2015</i>	<i>2016</i>	<i>2017</i>	<i>2018</i>	<i>2019</i>	<i>2020</i>	TOTAL
Fatal Accident	230	241	305	248	221	270	243	212	37	54	78	2141
Grievous Accident	32	66	63	54	60	64	76	11	60	68	11	565
Simple Injury Accident	16	28	24	17	25	24	10	1	11	3	19	178
Motor Collision	24	31	37	17	16	12	12	9	31	12	23	224

In terms of the events by accident severity for the last 11 years in Dhaka (Table 5), it was understood that the total rear-end road accident was 559 and total car-pedestrian impact was 1729. This percentage indicated that pedestrians were the most affected by the car crash accident. There were many reasons for pedestrians to have an accident. The impact object could be cars of other road users. The mass traffic environment might be the main reason for the high accident rate of pedestrians. Most pedestrians did not follow traffic rules and did not use sidewalks. They crossed the road wherever they wanted. Pedestrians were more likely to have accidents due to non-compliance with these rules. The record of the last 11 years showed that pedestrians were the most affected by 60%. Most of the drivers in Bangladesh did not follow the traffic rules properly. Mostly they did

not have a driving license and they were at a young age (Under 18 years old). For which they might not have the right knowledge to drive a vehicle properly. In the last 11 years, the rear-end accident case made up 19% of the total. In the accident involved with one car, the vehicle-pedestrian impact was the most. Meanwhile, in multiple car impacts, the rear impacts were the most.

Table 5. Events by impact type and year

IMPACT TYPE	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	TOTAL
Head On	6	0	0	19	0	0	0	2	6	10	3	46
Rear End	114	103	78	47	55	50	50	2	30	24	6	559
Right Angle	7	8	6	2	1	3	0	2	2	4	2	37
Side Swipe	3	7	18	22	17	23	13	7	25	21	1	157
Overturned Vehicle	1	5	4	4	5	11	2	2	1	4	6	45
Hit Object in Road	3	7	3	5	5	7	2	0	7	1	0	40
Hit Object Off Road	7	2	2	2	4	3	4	1	2	4	3	34
Hit Parked Vehicle	22	5	21	7	12	6	7	1	5	4	2	92
Hit Pedestrian	196	200	255	217	196	243	244	4	44	52	76	1729
Hit Animal	2	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	6
Other	12	19	19	5	4	8	6	3	13	15	20	124

Conclusion

The main objective of this study is to find out the last 11 years (2010-2020) road accident case data and Dhaka Road accident case data. Results show the accidents by impact type in the percentage of Dhaka. This indicates that most of the accidents caused by pedestrians are about 60% during the last 11 years. Most pedestrians do not notice pedestrians at the zebra crossing. Besides, 85% pedestrians crossed the road breaking the rules. The human factor is the main cause of the car crash, which accounts for more than 95% of the accidents. In addition, faulty vehicles, incompetent and unlicensed drivers, illegal market on the roads, illegal installations, occasional digging of roads without using alternative roads, adulteration of oil used in vehicles and lack of

necessary dividers in the roads are causing road accidents. So, drivers of buses and trucks need to be trained institutionally to develop their driving skills. Though the injury consequence is not much, the rear impact occupies the most percentage. If all vehicles are brought under the automatic monitoring system for the development of digital Bangladesh, road accidents will be reduced at a significant rate and civic life and resources will be saved.

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